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The European Union's Externalisation Policy in the Field of Migration and Asylum: Turkey as a Case Study

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List of Abbreviations

ACP-EU	African, Caribbean and Pacific-European Union
AFSJ	Area of Freedom, Security and Justice
AMIF	Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund
APD	Accession Partnership Document
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration Programme
CAMM	Common Agendas for Migration and Mobility
CEAS	Common European Asylum System
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CSO-LA	Civil Society Organisations and Local Authorities Programme
DCI	Development Cooperation Instruments
DG	Directorate General
DI	Differentiated Integration
EASO	European Asylum Support Office
EC	European Commission
ECHO	European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDF	European Development Fund
EEAS	European External Action Service
EIDHR	European Instrument for Democracy and Human Rights
ENI	European Neighbourhood Instrument
ENP	European Neighbourhood Policy
EP	European Parliament
EU	European Union
EURA	European Union Readmission Agreement
EUROPOL	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation
EUTRA	EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement
EUTS	EU-Turkey Statement
FRIT	Facility for Refugees in Turkey
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
GAM	Global Approach to Migration
GAMM	Global Approach to Migration and Mobility
IcSP	Instrument contributing to Stability and Peace
IO	Intergovernmental Organisation

IPA	Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance
ISF	Internal Security Fund
JAP	Joint Action Plan
JHA	Justice and Home Affairs
LFIP	Law on Foreigners and International Protection
MLG	Multilevel Governance
MobP	Mobility Partnership
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MS	Member States
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
NPAA	National Action Programmes for adopting the EU Acquis
PCA	Partnership and Cooperation Agreements
PI	Partnership Instrument
RESPOND	Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project
RPP	Regional Protection Programmes
RDPP	Regional Development and Protection Programme
TCN	Third-Country Nationals
WP	Work Package

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About the Project

RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (hereafter RESPOND) is a three-year project (2017–2020) that is funded by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon2020 Programme to enhance the governance capacity and policy coherence of the European Union (EU), its Member States and neighbours.

RESPOND is a comprehensive study of migration governance in the wake of the 2015 refugee crisis, one of the biggest challenges the Union has faced since its establishment. The crisis foregrounded the vulnerability of European borders, the tenuous jurisdiction of the Schengen system and broad problems in the multilevel governance of migration and integration. One of the most visible impacts of the refugee crisis has been the polarization of politics within the EU Member States (MS) and the (in)coherence in the Member States' response policies to the crisis.

Bringing together 14 partners from 7 disciplines, RESPOND aims to:

- provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research;
- critically analyse governance practices to enhance the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its Member States and third countries.

RESPOND is a comprehensive study of migration governance in the wake of the 2015 refugee crisis. The project probes policy-making processes and policy (in)coherence through comparative research in the source, transit, and destination countries.

RESPOND addresses how policy (in)coherence between the EU and its MS and between states differentially positioned as transit, hosting and source countries affects migration governance. Specifically, we will analyse the reasons behind the apparent policy incoherence by delineating interactions and outcomes between national refugee systems and the EU.

RESPOND studies migration governance through a narrative that is constructed along with five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and is designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impact and the responses of affected actors.

The work plan is organized around 11 work packages (WPs) – of which 8 have research tasks. The project also includes two WPs to organize impact-related activities targeting different audiences, including the scientific community, policy actors and the general public.

Executive Summary

This report is part of the RESPOND Project's Work Package 6 (WP6), titled 'Conflicting Europeanisation',¹ which focuses on the internal and external dynamics of the European Union's (EU) migration and asylum policy. In this framework, WP6 examines how the recent migration crisis has affected the future of European integration. It analyses the main parameters of divergence in migration governance and explores how these could impinge on the future course that EU integration takes. This report is prepared as 'D6.2: Externalisation of Europeanisation' and is one of the deliverables of the WP6.

The external dimension of the EU's migration and asylum policy emerged as a central policy nexus in the wake of the European migration crisis in 2015. While the dramatic increase in the number of entries by asylum seekers and irregular migrants again underscored the link between forced and irregular migration, it paved the way for a political and legitimisation crisis within the EU. Most EU Member States' showed a lack of political will for solidarity-based responses and safe reception conditions for those in need of international protection. The result was that a genuine humanitarian crisis turned into an existential crisis for the Union itself. It also created a significant impact on the EU's externalisation policy. This report analyses the EU's externalisation policy in migration and asylum since the 1990s, with a specific focus on the post-2015 period. By using the process-tracing method, it demonstrates the development of this policy field in the critical periods (1990–2003, 2004–2014 and 2015–present). The report notes how the year 2015 has been a key turning point, as crisis response and differentiated externalisation have become the 'new normal', reflected in the EU's New Pact on Migration and Asylum (the EU Pact), adopted in September 2020. Since 2015, rather than formal and standardised cooperation with third countries, the EU has been adopting more tailor-made, informal, flexible, and differentiated externalisation strategies. Against this backdrop, the report analyses external differentiation in the migration and asylum fields in the case of Turkey. Indeed, Turkey is something of a test case concerning continuities and changes in the EU's externalisation policy, with implications for the future as well. The report details both the historical context and more recent developments, such as the EU–Turkey Statement (2016), which was arguably the first instance of the EU's move to a more differentiated mode of externalisation in migration governance.

The report notes that migration and asylum policy have risen to the top of the EU's externalisation agenda. It is also contextually linked to the broader institutionalisation of the EU, becoming a state-like system with the intention to demarcate clear external borders, as well as a sharper distinction between the domestic and foreign policy fields. Differentiated integration comes into play as a compromise method to balance the Member States' differentiated national interests and preferences.

The report proceeds as follows: First, it provides a brief discussion on the conceptual part. It reviews the main instruments for the cooperation with third countries adopted by the EU to tackle the multiple dimensions of the migration phenomenon and control. Then, it focuses on Turkey as a case study for examining the usage of the external form of differentiated and wraps this up by linking the whole discussion with the Europeanisation debate. Finally, the conclusion contributes to the debate on the configuration and impact of EU cooperation with third countries in migration and proposes a set of concrete recommendations for further action.

¹ Further information about the RESPOND Project is available at: <https://www.respondmigration.com/> and the other deliverables of the WP6 are available at: <https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog> (Accessed 27 January 2021).

1. Introduction

The European Union's (EU) migration and asylum policies have confronted significant internal and external challenges in the last three decades. The considerable increase in the number of entries by asylum seekers and irregular migrants from 2015 provoked both a political and a legitimisation crisis. At the same time, EU cooperation with third countries to control migration and asylum has become a central aspect of the external dimension of EU migration and asylum policy.

Tackling irregular migration to effectively balance and manage migration flows has always been an essential component of the EU's external policy. The scale of irregular migration to the EU is actually quite limited compared to the total population.² However, it attracts disproportionate political attention, and the European migration crisis³ from 2015 gave new political impetus to the EU's migration and asylum agenda. The crisis also saw an expansion in the groups the EU seeks to control and block to include asylum seekers. In 2015, a total of 1,822,337 irregular crossings were recorded at the EU's external borders. Almost half of these — 885,386 — came via the maritime Eastern Mediterranean Route (Frontex, 2016: 16). In the same year, asylum applications reached a peak of 1,257,000, which was almost double that of 2014, according to Eurostat (2017).

The task of categorising and granting different legal statuses has been largely left to the southern EU Member States (MS), mainly Italy and Greece, where the so-called 'hotspot approach'⁴ of irregular migration management was adopted. However, this immediate action to assist frontline MS facing excessive migratory pressures at the EU's external borders did not work and the Blueprint Network⁵ developed by the EU's New Pact on Migration and Asylum (the EU Pact) as a limited remedy for those countries (European Commission, 2020a). There were also some internal attempts to respond to the increased entries, such as the

² Recent studies claim a range of figures, anywhere from 1.9 million to 3.8 million for the EU in 2008 (Kovacheva and Vogel, 2009: 7) and 2.9 million to 3.8 million in 2017 including irregular stays (Connor and Passel, 2019: 5; Spencer and Triandafyllidou, 2020: 2). It means that irregular migration makes up 0.4–0.8% of the total EU population of 447.7 million (Eurostat, 2020).

³ A range of descriptors have come into use to cover the crisis conditions that (mostly) Europe underwent in this period, including 'European refugee crisis' and 'European humanitarian refugee crisis' (Carrera et al., 2019), but also 'migration crisis' (Kalir and Cantat, 2020), European 'solidarity crisis' (Grimmel and Giang, 2017). Among these, 'European humanitarian refugee crisis' reflects the problematic aspects of Europe's and the EU's humanitarian responses. Given the consequences involved several migration categories, the term 'European migration crisis' is adopted in the present report.

⁴ This approach was developed by the European Commission as part of the immediate action to assist the MS located at the external EU border. It was presented in the European Agenda on Migration in May 2015. Accordingly, the operational support provided those MS (it is applied only to Italy and Greece) for registration, identification, fingerprinting and debriefing of asylum seekers, as well as return operations with the collaboration of EASO, Frontex, Europol and Eurojust. Further information is available at: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/what-we-do/networks/european_migration_network/glossary_search/hotspot-approach_en (Accessed 3 September 2020).

⁵ The Blueprint Network gathering the MSs, the relevant EU Agencies and the EEAS as a platform for information exchange with specific EU countries and non-EU countries. It will support decisions to deploy in the MSs in need more specific crisis tools such as hotspots, financial assistance, operational support (European Commission, 2020a).

comprehensive reform of the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) and the 'relocation mechanism' to share responsibilities among the MS. However, these attempts have also not worked and provoked further political and legitimisation crises within the EU. The lack of political will among most of the MS and the absence of solidarity-based responses and safe reception conditions resulted in a genuine humanitarian crisis. It has also had severe adverse effects on Europeanisation and has become an existential crisis for the Union itself. Once again, European policy-making in the face of the crisis has shown that one size fits none and thrown into sharp relief the different interests, security perceptions, and sensibilities of the individual MS.

On the other hand, the external dimension of EU immigration and asylum policy became an essential policy domain due to the migration pressures outside EU borders. This external area refers to the external borders and beyond, where the EU governance operates through externalisation and cooperation with the third countries. The EU has been developing externalisation of its migration and asylum policies since the early 1990s. The focus of EU decision-making in this domain has been moving increasingly beyond European borders, requiring cooperation agreements with third countries and convincing them to provide some incentives to control migration and asylum. After abolishing the internal borders through Schengen, the EU started increasingly to focus on tackling irregular migration and cooperating with third countries on readmission and return.

The process of externalisation has evolved through different periods, with the impact of particular historical events. The Syrian mass migration and large-scale migration flows in 2015/2016 have created significant consequences for the EU. Therefore, the EU's cooperation with the main transit countries has grown in importance, including Turkey — which has hosted the largest number of refugees in the world since 2014. The vast majority of these are Syrians — some 3.6 million are under temporary protection in Turkey at present, which amount to 64.4% of the total displaced Syrian population (UNHCR, 2020a). Turkey also hosts around 370,000 refugees and asylum seekers of other nationalities under international protection (Ibid.).

Turkey has had a long and complicated relationship with the EU. Its official candidate status was granted in 1999, and formal membership negotiations were launched in 2005. Thus, Turkey offers a case study in both Europeanisation and externalisation regarding migration and asylum policies. Turkey also exemplifies the report's central argument—namely, that there has been extensive differentiated integration and externalisation in EU migration governance in the last decade.

This report analyses the EU's externalisation policy in migration and asylum since the 1990s with a particular focus on the period after 2015. It traces the evolution of the EU's approach across three main time-periods: 1990–2003, 2004–2014, and 2015–present. The report notes how the year 2015 has been a critical turning point, as crisis response and differentiated externalisation have become the 'new normal', reflected in the EU Pact adopted in September 2020. Since 2015, rather than formal and standardised cooperation with third countries, the EU has been adopting more tailor-made, informal, flexible, and differentiated externalisation strategies. Against this backdrop, the report analyses external differentiation in the migration and asylum fields in the case of Turkey. Indeed, Turkey is something of a test case concerning continuities and changes in the EU's externalisation policy, with implications for the future as well.

The report reveals that the differentiated externalisation is partly the impact of historical developments and external factors such as crises and responses to third countries' differentiated demands. The target countries of the EU's externalisation are not passive policy receivers, and they use migration as a foreign policy tool, particularly after seeing its

importance for the EU after 2015. However, as will be discussed in the conceptual part, the existing literature on EU externalisation treats migration and asylum policy as a unidirectional flow from the EU to target countries, portrayed as passive recipients. Thus, the interaction among the EU actors and the non-EU countries and the third countries' responses remains understudied.

In this regard, this report attempts to re-contextualise the EU's externalisation policy in migration and asylum. It is a fact that the EU has been changing its strategy and moving away from established decision-making rules and institutional principles. The ongoing strategy of extra-Treaty cooperation and instruments can be seen as constitutional challenges to the EU, which is evaluated as de-constitutionalization or de-Europeanisation. Still, they can just as well be seen as new strategies for problem-solving under the rubric of 'crisis'. There are new instruments and strategies since 2015, such as statements, deals, compacts, joint actions, joint declarations that fall outside the EU Treaties, escaping the EU general principles, sidelining the European Parliament and the Court of Justice of the EU (CJEU). These policy arrangements provide flexibility regarding the challenges and responses coming from third countries. The report argues that this new differentiated strategy has been developed to avoid deadlock and respond to the actual demands in migration policy with tailor-made, flexible policy arrangements and actions become that are increasingly becoming the 'new normal'.

The main finding is that the EU continues to pursue established externalisation strategies regarding migration and asylum, but its role and weight have increased and has become more differentiated since 2015. In this framework, the report details Turkey's response and position from a critical perspective regarding externalisation and conditionality. It also aims to understand what this strategic option implies in terms of costs, benefits, and externalisation effectiveness in cooperation with Turkey. It provides a historical perspective to see the changes after the crisis and how crisis politics turn into a common norm. Although there has always been a certain degree of differentiation for the MS and third countries, the crisis provided a new justification to act outside Community orthodoxy. The state of emergency and its exceptions due to the crisis period turned into the 'new normal'. It is also seen that in addition to the long-lasting main focus of the externalisation policy in this field—irregular migration and cooperating with third countries on readmission and return—the asylum aspect also became more visible and justified as a part of control mechanisms.

The research benefits from the historical institutionalist approach and applies the process-tracing method, thereby studying causal mechanisms that link causes with outcomes, specifically how a cause(s) contributes to producing an outcome. In particular, the research adopts the "explaining-outcome process-tracing" approach and aims to explain a "puzzling historical outcome" without attempting to generalize the findings (Beach and Pedersen, 2013: 11). It focuses on a single case study (Turkey) and compiles data from a variety of sources to provide comprehensive insights into policies, regulations, and practices regarding the externalisation policy of the EU in the field of migration and asylum. The discussion of politics and legal regulations are based on document analyses of policy and legislative materials. The data comprises a range of different documents that inform about the EU's migration policy and the bilateral documents between the EU and Turkey. The bilateral and multilateral documents between the EU and Turkey, such as the EU–Turkey Readmission Agreement (EUTRA, 2013) the EU–Turkey Statement (EUTS, European Council, 2016a), were also analysed deeply.

The report proceeds as follows: First, it provides a brief discussion on the conceptual part. It reviews the main instruments for the cooperation with third countries adopted by the EU to tackle the multiple dimensions of the migration phenomenon and control. Then, it focuses on Turkey as a case study for examining the usage of the external form of differentiated and wraps this up by linking the whole discussion with the Europeanisation debate. Finally, the conclusion

contributes to the debate on the configuration and impact of EU cooperation with third countries in migration and proposes a set of concrete recommendations for further action.

2. The Conceptual Framework: Europeanisation and Externalisation

The term 'Europeanisation' was first used during the early 1990s when it was defined as "an incremental process reorienting the direction and shape of politics to the degree that the European Community political and economic dynamics become part of the organisational logic or national logic of national politics and policy-making" (Ladrech, 1994: 70). More straightforwardly, it is a process where decisions made at the EU level define and shape policy at the domestic level (Vink, 2002: 1, 13). More recently, Radielli has defined Europeanisation more broadly as:

processes of (a) construction (b) diffusion and (c) institutionalisation of formal and informal rules, procedures, policy paradigms, styles, 'ways of doing things' and shared beliefs and norms which are first defined and consolidated in the making of EU public policy and politics and then incorporated in the logic of domestic discourse, identities, political structures, and public policies (Radielli, 2003: 30).

Within the field of European studies, the term has been used more broadly still. Here, it refers to the influence the EU can exercise beyond its territory by exporting forms of political organisation and governance to states not necessarily subject to prospective EU membership (Olsen, 2002: 924). It is, in this sense, closely linked to externalisation. Externalisation is a process by which non-EU countries wholly or partially adopt EU norms, policy instruments, policy programmes, procedures, institutions, and administrative agencies in the broader European neighbourhood (Lavenex and Uçarer, 2002; 2004).

By the 1990s, migration and asylum policy had become highly politicised for both the EU and its MS. Thus, cooperation with sending and transit countries on immigration and asylum policy rose quickly to the top of the EU agenda (Boswell, 2003: 619). Accordingly, the concept of 'externalisation' came to be linked to migration policy during the 2000s. Against this backdrop, Doukoure and Oger detailed how externalisation functions in migration governance as follows:

The reproduction of European internal migration policy at the external level entails burden-sharing in the policing of European borders with bordering countries and the setting up migration management policies in the countries of origin, particularly concerning illegal migration, in line with European interests. (Doukoure and Oger, 2007: 2).

The primary purpose of externalisation in migration policy is "to prevent migrants, including asylum seekers, from entering the legal jurisdictions or territories of [European] destination countries or regions or making them legally inadmissible without individually considering the merits of their protection claims" (Frelick et al., 2016: 193).

Externalisation is operationalized via two main approaches —namely, the 'remote control' and the 'root cause' approach. The first aims to keep potential migrants away and prevent them from reaching the EU border, given it is harder to expel unwanted migrants once they have arrived due to legal and humanitarian protections (Zapata Barrero, 2013: 10). The second approach focuses on pull and push factors and aims to reduce the push factors motivating people to leave the home country, mostly through providing development support. The 'remote

control' approach is reactive and aims to control migration movements once they have begun. Therefore, it is built around security-oriented restrictive measures. The root cause approach is proactive and development-focused, aiming to invest in preventive measures to tackle drivers of migration.⁶

Externalisation entails cooperation with third countries. In turn, cooperation has entailed an organisational model of power relations that instrumentalise third (especially transit or source) countries to adopt a Eurocentric approach. In general, EU externalisation policies aim to obtain third countries' support for migration control and management through incentives to keep the unwanted population within their territories. Such incentives can include logistical, financial, or political support or direct aid. Other measures involve more capacity-building, including readmission and incentive structures, economic and political support for migrant accommodation and removal (detention) centres or partnerships to combat irregular migration or to strengthen the capacity of immigration or asylum systems in third countries (Frelick et al., 2016: 195).

The literature on externalisation has generally foregrounded the EU's power vis-à-vis relatively weak target countries, which are portrayed as passive recipients of EU policy. Thus, the field has mostly neglected the *agency of target countries* in their dynamic interactions with the EU —especially their willingness and ability *to counter and negotiate*. Instead, to properly understand the interaction between EU institutions, the MS, and the third countries, a “three-level game” analytical frame is required (Reslow and Vink, 2015). Here, conditionality⁷ should also be analysed from non-EU countries' perspective to gain insight into their cost-benefit calculations (Carrera et al., 2019: 10). Some studies have indeed offered finer-grained analyses that assess the responses of target countries to EU externalisation policy and theorise the relationship between migration and foreign policy (Teitelbaum, 1984; Mitchell, 1989; Geddes, 2009; Greenhill, 2010; İçduygu and Aksel, 2014; Wolff 2014; Carrera et al., 2016; Üstübeci and İçduygu, 2018; Gökalp Aras, 2019a). In particular, the case of Syrian mass migration and EU–Turkey relations casts into sharp relief the enduring salience of Teitelbaum's (1984: 433) established insight on how mass migration can be used by sending and receiving countries as a tool to achieve foreign policy objectives by destabilising or embarrassing adversaries. Greenhill (2010) has proposed the concept of “coercive engineered migration (CEM)” to capture this dynamic. Tsourapas uses “coercive and cooperative migration diplomacy” (Tsourapas, 2017).

Greenhill has systematically elaborated the relationship between foreign policy and mass-migration response. She defines ‘CEM’ or ‘migration-driven coercion’ as “cross-border population movements that are deliberately created or manipulated often by weak states or non-state actors to induce political, military and/or economic concessions from a target state, states or international organisations” (Greenhill, 2010: 13). She highlights how weak actors view migration crises as a necessary precursor to negotiations with their more powerful counterparts (Ibid.: 28). Greenhill's framework offers significant analytical purchase in evaluating the diplomatic interplay involved in EU externalisation and in challenging the assumed passivity of target countries in this relationship. Greenhill defines ‘opportunistic states’ as a subcategory of actors employing migration-driven coercion who play no direct role in creating migration crises but exploit them to pursue policy goals. For instance, the

⁶ In parallel, Papadopoulou (2007: 98) draws strategies of EU externalisation in the field of migration into three categories — namely, ‘remote control’, ‘remote protection’, and ‘capacity-building’.

⁷ Defined as the “EU pays the reward if the target government complies with the conditions and withholds the reward if it fails to comply” (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier, 2004: 663).

opportunist might threaten to close its borders unless targets take desired actions or offer side-payments, or—as has been the case with Turkey—to open them, thereby producing a humanitarian emergency. Opportunists sometimes offer to alleviate existing crises in exchange for political or monetary pay-offs (Ibid.: 30–31).

Rather than being a passive policy receiver, Ankara's policy decisions in this field have been geared towards the rational achievement of strategic aims, which is to say that instrumental considerations were front and centre. In this vein, Juliette Tolay (2012) defines Turkey's "non-traditional form of Europeanization" as an instance of what she calls "critical Europeanization". Saime Özçürümez and Nazlı Şenses (2011: 233) discuss the capacity of the target countries to resist the EU's externalisation policies. In Turkey's case, they argue that the Europeanisation and externalisation of migration policy in Turkey reflects a process of "absorption with reservations". Absorption has occurred despite the significant developments and reforms since 1999 in irregular migration, while adaptation has appeared without actual modification to the essential structures or changes in the logic of political behaviour (Ibid.: 246–247). Turkey has always tried to resist EU conditionality, and various incentives are used such as membership, visa liberalisation, financial aids for convincing asymmetric costs and benefits as has been the case in other third countries (Rumelili, 2004).

The EU and Turkey have *both* instrumentalised the Syrian mass migration and the European humanitarian refugee crises. At the same time, these crises have created a political and legitimation crisis within the EU. Additionally, the crisis has allowed both sides to increasingly approach policy through the lens of 'securitisation' and adopt exceptional policy actions. Buzan and Waever define securitisation as "the discursive process through which an intersubjective understanding is constructed within a political community to treat something as an existential threat to a valued referent object and to enable a call for urgent and exceptional measures to deal with the threat" (2003: 491).

Securitisation is thus a 'speech act' that fulfils three critical rhetorical criteria. The first is the discursive process portraying a problem as an 'existential threat'—e.g., irregular transit migration or mass influxes of asylum seekers—as a part of a 'claim' action. The second is the demand for the right to take extraordinary countermeasures to combat the socially constructed threat. Not all actors can securitise an issue effectively since institutional and political authority is required.

Since securitisation is a speech act that labels something as a threat and problem of supreme priority, the third rhetorical criterion is the justification of rule-breaking behaviours to combat the existential threat. For example, as a part of the second criteria, the European Council (the European Council members) and Turkey negotiated the EUTS using the 'crisis' as a justification. With this decision, the EU ignored the principle of inter-institutional balance in the EU Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (AFSJ) and the European Parliament's (EP) role as co-legislator for the conclusion of international agreements created by the Lisbon Treaty. The role of the CJEU was also by-passed with this justification. Gürkan and Coman (2020) argue that despite the fact that the agreement deeply contradicts fundamental EU values and norms, the EUTS is the outcome of the "ideational and power struggles between supranational and intergovernmental institutions of the EU. In other words, the struggles between the normative power and its arguments and the security concerns of the MS from intergovernmentalist perspective.

The "crisis" was instrumentalised to justify the demand for the right to take countermeasures and the required authority where crisis labelling underpinned invocation of a state of exception. The crisis itself provided the opportunity to normalize the conceptions of political authority and crisis policy-making. In this way, the third criterion—justifying rule-breaking behaviours to combat the existential threat—was foregrounded. For example, in the EU Pact, the

Commission proposes a new 'border procedure' and mentions the possible increase of 'detention' as a standard approach (European Commission, 2020a). The EU Pact was published just several months after the Turkey-Greece border 'tragedy' of February 2020 and the Moria refugee camp disaster⁸ in September 2020. It can also be seen as an effort to secure audience acceptance and legitimacy to implement measures beyond daily routines.

Since 2015, crisis and securitisation discourse and differentiated integration concerning internal (Europeanisation) and external (externalisation) dimensions in the field of migration and asylum have heightened. As will be analysed in the section on historical developments, the EU Pact (2020) also shows that differentiated integration has become a 'new normal' vis-à-vis cooperation with third countries in the external area. Okyay et al. (2020: 2) argues that the "growing weight given to external cooperation leads to increasing participation by non-member states in EU migration and asylum policy, in both regulatory and organisational terms, constituting instances of external differentiation". The EU has used differentiated integration as a method to respond to crises such as the 2008 Great Recession and the Euro crisis, Brexit, the European humanitarian refugee crisis and the recent Covid-19 global pandemic. This method provides the EU and the MS the needed flexibility to overcome policy deadlocks.

Differentiated integration can be seen as a flexible form of integration under a range of labels such as 'multi-speed', multi-tier' or 'core Europe', 'variable geometry', 'l'Europe à la carte' and 'differentiated integration'. The common point for all these flexible integration frames is that MS and non-EU states converge with different speeds in different EU policy areas with 'ins' and 'outs'. Differentiated integration is not a new method. It has been part of discussions on European integration since the 1970s and intensified during the 1990s and in the recent 'refugee crisis' (Holzinger and Schimmelfennig, 2012).

Like externalisation, the first discussions of differentiated integration were mainly among MS and related to the internal dimension. However, due to the emerging interdependencies with third countries, it has also become increasingly reflected in externalisation policy. In this context, it refers to the MS' right to 'opt-out' and third countries' possibility to 'opt-in' to policy proposals in the external area. Stubb (1996) provided a three-way classification for various kinds of differentiation —namely, 'temporal' (related to time), 'territorial' (space) and 'sectoral' differentiation (policy fields). Holzinger and Schimmelfennig (2012: 9) add three more categories to Stubb's framework, emphasising the external dimension of the differentiated integration as "member states vs non-member states/areas outside the EU territory". Leuffen and colleagues (2013) distinguish between 'internal' and 'external' differentiation. Here, internal differentiation refers to the exceptions that MS carve out from EU law, while external differentiation refers to a situation in which third countries import some European rules accompanied by compensation payments. Schimmelfennig and colleagues (2015: 765) have developed this external dimension with their "vertical and horizontal differentiation" classification. While vertical differentiation refers to policy areas that have been integrated at different speeds and reached different centralisation levels over time, horizontal differentiation relates to the territorial dimension.

Lavenex argues that the dynamics of the external form of differentiated integration are predominantly sector-specific and functionalist (2015: 836). The observation has become more salient since 2015 given the classic 'Community Method' has provided insufficient policy flexibility, and we observe power shifts among the EU's decision-making actors— namely, the Council, the Parliament and the Commission. Therefore, as Lavenex (2015) argues, foreign

⁸ Further information is available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/09/09/world/europe/fire-refugee-camp-lesbos-moria.html> (Accessed 3 February 2021).

policy and functionalist approaches have become more visible. The EU's regulatory extension results from direct foreign policy initiatives such as the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) and sector-specific policy diffusions, such as migration and asylum policy.

Also, rather than the EU's central foreign policy institutions, trans-governmental bodies such as the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) and the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol) support cooperation with third countries in migration and asylum. In particular, Frontex operates in a highly politicised space in which state sovereignty is critical, but it has been involved in trans-governmental networking—including with Turkey through the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)—since 2012. Lavenex argues that “while the EU's central decision-making bodies exclude their participation, the EU's trans-governmental layer, in particular, the sector-specific ones provide an alternative for the ‘Community Method’ of European integration” (2015: 839).

As in the predominant Europeanisation and externalisation discussions, differentiated integration also implies incentives for the external form of differentiation. The EU strives in this way to export its policies to third countries by inducing them to join initiatives in specific sectors through incentives (Holzinger and Tosun, 2019: 643). In general, financial incentives are provided to third countries in an attempt to induce them to align their policies with the EU.

The incentives are also dependent on which EU rules are adopted by non-member states, and therefore which bargaining forms apply accordingly. There is a positive relationship here—the denser the interdependence in a given policy field, the greater the bargaining power of the EU. However, in some cases, the same applies to third countries. The recent crisis period—especially during the European refugee crisis—saw the bargaining power of the transit and source countries such as Turkey grow. The higher the financial incentives provided to the related countries. The more is at stake for the EU, the greater the financial incentives the European Commission will need to offer to finance reforms or actions in line with EU standards. The political preference of the EU is to integrate its neighbourhood by offering financial incentives for the implementation of reforms. If we look at the debate on differentiated integration, the term ‘incentives’ (incentivising) has been prominent compared to more established frames like ‘conditionality’ and ‘rewards’. However, logic and functionality remain the same. It appears as “a strategic game between EU actors seeking further integration on the one hand, and exemption-seeking member states or compensation-seeking non-members on the other hand” (Holzinger and Tosun, 2019: 646). The adoption of EU rules entails adjustment costs for the target governments (Ibid.). Thus, the EU is willing to balance these costs with attractive incentives, such as direct budget support (Ibid.: 652).

Differentiated externalisation also provides a better understanding of EU relations with third countries with no membership plans. As will be discussed later, the membership dimension has also become blurry and in line with a new emphasis on differentiated integration, rather than full membership, strong cooperation in specific sectors and differentiated membership are front and centre in policy discussions. This bargaining power remains mainly policy-specific and is dependent on the interdependence at play in a given policy area.

3. The Development of the EU External Dimension in the Field of Migration and Asylum

EU externalisation in migration and asylum embraces different tools and strategies, ranging from unilateral to bilateral to multilateral and formal and informal agreements and partnerships with private actors. As discussed in the conceptual part, direct intervention and preventive policies are supported with more indirect actions (e.g., providing support, development

assistance and capacity-building activities) to cooperate with third countries. Although the report focuses mainly on post-2015 developments, it is crucial to briefly recall the history of externalisation policies in migration and analyse the existing instruments.

The externalisation of EU migration policy has evolved in the wake of significant developments and through several key phases. Lavenex (2006) outlines three major empirical milestones: (1) the Schengen Agreement of 1990; (2) the ‘safe third country rule’ that became prominent in the Dublin Regulation of 1990; and (3) the readmission agreements. Halvik (2019: 17) periodizes these phases as follows: 1990–2003 (Schengen), 2004–2014 (Dublin) and 2015–2019 (when third countries were brought into EU policy-making through readmission agreements). This report concurs that the most recent period began in 2015 with the European humanitarian refugee crisis. This marked a new era with increased differentiated integration both internally and externally. After 2015, cooperation with third countries became one of the central elements of the externalisation in this field, leading to increased participation of non-EU members in this policy field and differentiated integration. Some old mechanisms and approaches have continued to be supported within crisis-based management and ad-hoc tools, which seems to have become the new normal, given the exceptional actions foreshadowed in the EU Pact (2020).

The EU’s instruments regarding cooperation with third countries in the field of immigration and asylum can be classified into three groups: “**political instruments**”, “**legal instruments**”, and “**operational instruments**” (IPOL, 2015). Departing from their categorisation, I added one more category as a part of instruments: financial instruments.

Table 1: Instruments of the External Dimension of EU Migration and Asylum Policies

Political Instruments	Legal Instruments	Operational Instruments	Financial Instruments
Regional dialogues	Migration clauses in ‘global agreements’.	Regional Protection Programmes and Regional Development and Protection Programmes	European Development Fund (EDF) Development Cooperation Instruments (DCI)
Bilateral dialogues	Specific international agreements on migration (Readmission Agreements, Visa Liberalisation Agreements)	Frontex Working Arrangements	European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI)
Mobility Partnerships (MobPs)		European Asylum Support Office (EASO) cooperation with third countries	The Instrument of Pre-accession (IPA)

Common Agendas for Migration and Mobility (CAMMs)			Civil Society Organisations and Local Authorities Programme (CSO-LA) Global Public Goods and Challenges Programme European Instrument for Democracy and Human Rights (EIDHR) Instrument contributing to Stability and Peace (IcSP)
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Source: Prepared by the author based on IPOL. 2015. *EU Cooperation with Third Countries in the Field of Migration Study*. Available at: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/supporting-analyses> (Accessed 18 October 2020).

Political instruments refer to the **regional dialogues** covering the main regions of origin and transit of migration flows. They are based on the identification of mutual interests and concerns, the exchange of good practices and data, and a commitment to deepen the cooperation launched with a political declaration adopted at ministerial level with the participation of the MS and the European Commission (Ibid.). In terms of spatial aspect, they cover the main regions of origin and transit of migration identified in the Prague Process (2009), the Budapest Process (2013), the Eastern Partnership (2011), the Rabat Process (2006), the Africa-EU Migration and Mobility Dialogue (2006), the African, Caribbean and Pacific (ACP)-EU Migration Dialogue (2010), and the Khartoum Process (2014). They are generally launched through a political declaration adopted at the ministerial level, with the European Commission's participation, or sometimes based on a declaration from the Heads of State and Government meetings as it was the case for the EUTS (2016).

In addition to the regional dialogues, some bilateral dialogues are based on the dialogues between the EU and the country concerned on Justice and Home Affairs (JHA) related issues in migration and asylum. Most bilateral dialogues are based on technical cooperation on readmission and related incentives such as visa liberation agreements. These dialogues are based on the Stabilisation and Association Agreements, such as with Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro, Serbia or the Ankara Association Agreement (1963), which is the basis for Turkey (IPOL, 2015: 28). There are also Partnership and Cooperation Agreements (PCAs) with Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine and the Dialogue on Migration launched with Russia (2011). The Euro-Mediterranean Association agreements with Morocco, Tunisia, Jordan and Lebanon are the other samples (Ibid.). The EU also benefits from other specific bilateral dialogues based on technical cooperation or readmission agreements and visa dialogues such as the EUTRA (2013) and the Roadmap Towards a Visa-Free Regime with Turkey (2013), the **Mobility Partnerships (MobPs)** and the **Common Agendas for Migration and Mobility (CAMM)** as part of the political instruments.

Finally, as a part of the bilateral dialogues of the political instruments, the EU Compacts should be mentioned. They are also used interchangeably with EU partnerships. The target countries for the compacts are not surprising, but the main source and transit countries. The first compacts were signed with Jordan (2016–2018) and Lebanon (2016–2020), followed by Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Mali and Ethiopia, as well as Tunisia and Libya (European Council, 2016b). Accordingly, the compacts focus on strengthening the host countries' economic resilience while enhancing Syrian refugees' economic opportunities through increased protection and access to employment and quality education (Ibid.). According to the EU, the compacts are the technical negotiations' outcomes for a fully-fledged formal agreement (European Commission, 2016b). They provide an appropriate and safe environment for refugees and displaced persons supported by financial instruments (Ibid.). Similarly, the EUTS can be seen

as a special compact with Turkey—a form of crisis-based ad-hoc cooperation with return and readmission dimensions.

There are migration clauses in ‘global agreements’ such as association agreements and cooperation agreements regarding the classification of **the legal instrument**. Briefly, it can be said that the EU has included migration-related clauses into international agreements since the 1990s as the starting point of the EU cooperation with third countries on migration issues. The majority of them were mainly related to the readmission of irregular migration, which can be seen as the pioneers of the **EU Readmission Agreements (EURAs)**. These migration-related clauses within the comprehensive international agreements were followed by the **‘specific international agreements on migration’** along with **visa facilitation** and **visa waiver agreements**.

As a part of operational instruments, the **regional protection programmes** and the **regional development and protection programmes** function as root-causes or development-focused approaches. Rather than externalisation per se, they foresee the development of international protection in the target countries. The EU encourages third countries to develop their asylum system to better protect refugees through these programmes (IPOL, 2015). Due to the relatively better and improved conditions, the argument goes, fewer asylum seekers will continue to their migratory journey to the EU may even be able to return to third countries since they will be considered ‘safe’.

Although the purpose is the same as the other instruments, the strategy is different. These instruments are called ‘Regional Protection Programmes’ (RPPs), and they aim to enhance the protection capacity of third countries. In the wake of the Syrian mass migration in 2012, a new model of RPPs was developed and named as Regional Development and Protection Programme (RDPP). They are also mentioned as part of the European Agenda on Migration. The other two instruments of the operational dimension (the working Agreements of Frontex and EASO) will be mentioned in the following section.

Along with the other instruments, financial instruments are also available as part of the EU external cooperation in migration and asylum through some of the old channels and the new and specific ones regarding the policy field. They provide an opportunity for different EU policies such as migration and asylum policy, international development cooperation, external policy or humanitarian aid policy. Besides, there are some exceptions or differentiated country-specific instruments like the €6 billion allocated for Turkey as a part of the Joint Action Plan (JAP) in 2015 and the EUTS in 2016.

Figure 1: Main instruments for EU external cooperation 2014–2020

Source: IPOL. 2015. *EU Cooperation with Third Countries in the Field of Migration Study*. Available at: <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/supporting-analyses> (Accessed 18 October 2020), p. 53.

As the common point, the most important operational areas of the above-mentioned financial instruments are related to irregular migration, readmissions and returns and asylum and regional protection programmes. In terms of modalities, capacity-building and sometimes equipment supply (particularly for border management) constitute the most significant share. In addition to these funds, there are the European Refugee Fund, the European Return Fund and the European Fund for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals. These were merged into the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF), the Internal Security Fund (ISF/ Border and Visa& ISF Police), and the Pan-African Partnership Instrument with the 2014–2020 multi-year budget. Finally, the European External Action Service (EEAS) also has the so-called Partnership Instrument (PI).

The other instruments and the related programmes will be detailed in the relevant period under discussion below. Along with the thematic overview, the three phases of the development of the EU's externalisation in migration and asylum are laid out, beginning with the first phase (1990–2003).

3.1. The First Phase: The Emergence of the Legal and Institutional Framework of Externalisation (1990–2003)

The most important precursor to the first phase was the Schengen Agreement (1985),⁹ which abolished all the internal borders within the Schengen Area¹⁰ and drew the lines between internal and external in European affairs. The Dublin Convention (1990)¹¹ and the ‘safe third country rule’ then developed as the internal readmission mechanism of the EU, despite being in line with established international principles. However, the Dublin mechanism created uneven distribution of asylum seekers among the MS. In particular, the frontline countries were increasingly overloaded, with many delays and problems, such as Greece’s case, particularly after the EUTS. Even though the Convention and the Dublin Regulation were revised in 2011 and 2015, the Dublin system faced further problems after the European humanitarian refugee crisis in 2015 and was abolished by the EU Pact in 2020.

However, it was essential to create a safe third country rule regarding the EU’s return policy and contribute to closer cooperation with the source and transit countries concerning the external dimension. Thus, these early moves were combined with efforts to establish readmission obligations with neighbouring states considered ‘safe countries’. In the same period, the Amsterdam Treaty (1997),¹² the Tampere Summit of 1999, the establishment of the CEAS in 1999 and the incorporation of the Schengen Agreement into EU law in 1999 were other significant developments. The Amsterdam Treaty (1997) was a crucial development because the migration and asylum issues were moved into the EU legislation from national governments, and the European Commission’s responsibilities regarding the JHA were expanded. Thus, this policy field was granted a supranational character as an important step in the institutionalisation of externalisation.

Followingly, the Tampere Summit (1999) provided operational details, and the foreseen provisions by the Amsterdam Treaty became more concrete and operational with the establishment of the CEAS with its external action. At the Seville Summit (2002), it was decided to include migration management and readmission clauses in every form of cooperation negotiated and implemented with third countries. In order to convince third countries for cooperation agreements, different types of incentives have been introduced.

⁹ The full text of the Convention on Implementing the Schengen Agreement is available at: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42000A0922\(02\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42000A0922(02)&from=EN) (Accessed 14 November 2020).

¹⁰ Within this ‘area’, free movement is allowed for the more than 400 million EU citizens, as well as many non-EU nationals present on EU territory.

¹¹ The Convention on Determining the State Responsible for Examining Applications for Asylum Lodged in one of the Member States of the European Communities (Dublin) is available at: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:41997A0819\(01\)&from=EN](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:41997A0819(01)&from=EN) (Accessed 14 November 2020).

¹² The Treaty of Amsterdam amending the Treaty on European Union, the Treaties Establishing the European Communities and Certain Related Acts (1997) is available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:11997D/TXT&from=EN> (Accessed 14 November 2020).

3.2. The Second Phase: Emergence of the General Frame in External Action (2004–2014)

During the second period, the cooperation with the third countries intensified, and the most important policies of externalisation started to take shape. These were the ENP (2004, revised in 2011), the Global Approach to Migration (GAM),¹³ the EU Return Directive (2008)¹⁴ and the Mobility Partnerships (MobPs) that the EU commenced with eastern countries from 2007 onwards.

The ENP was designed to respond to new enlargement and migratory pressures from the south and east. The Barcelona Process was one of the first steps in this framework and foresaw cooperation with sixteen neighbouring countries, all of which were seen as potential core source or transit countries. The southern countries are Algeria, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Palestine,¹⁵ Syria (suspended by the EU since 2011) and Tunisia. The eastern ones are Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, the Republic of Moldova and Ukraine. The EU has readmission and visa liberation agreements, MobPs and other instruments with many of these countries. Russia and the EU have cross-border cooperation under the ENP, but—unlike the other countries—Russia is not a direct member of this policy area.

The ENP has been supported by the European Neighbourhood Instrument (ENI). The EU claims the ENI's new dimension will emphasise 'faster and more flexible' action, 'offering incentives for best performers', and 'allow for greater differentiation' (EU Neighbours, 2020). However, Capesciotti (2017: 34) argues that the ENP has already failed because it had reached its limits in serving the regional self-interests of the MS regarding security, economic opportunities and border control.

In the same year as the ENP was formed, the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) was established. Frontex is an essential institution in the implementation and structuring of externalisation in this field. Also, Article 79 (3) of the Lisbon Treaty (which entered into force in 2009) provides the other legal basis for the EU's return policy which has been a vital part of cooperation with the third countries. As a part of the operational instruments, Frontex develops its external action in border management, prioritising externalisation. Frontex cooperates actively with non-EU countries to ensure the implementation of the European integrated border management (IBM) system. So far, eighteen working arrangements have been completed with third countries.¹⁶

¹³ The full text of the European Commission Communication on the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (GAMM) is available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0743&from=EN> (Accessed 4 November 2020).

¹⁴ DIRECTIVE 2008/115/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals is available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0115&from=EN> (Accessed 4 September 2020).

¹⁵ Due to the special status of Palestine, the EU states that the ENP dimension will be conducted without prejudice of the MSs on this issue.

¹⁶ Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Canada, Cape Verde, CIS Border Troop Commanders, Georgia, Kosovo, MARRI, Moldova, Montenegro, Nigeria, Serbia, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, the Russian Federation, the United States, Turkey and Ukraine (Frontex, 2020a).

Frontex takes a role within Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (GAMM), the Mobility Partnerships (MobPs) and CAMMs and also directly as a part of the Khartoum, Rabat, and Budapest Processes, the Valetta Summit follow-up and other Commission-led initiatives. Since its establishment in 2004, it has been growing every year as its personnel, the scope of its mandate, and its budget have increased significantly. The increasing role of Frontex was again foregrounded in the EU Migration and Asylum Pact, in particular regarding return and readmission operations. Frontex also assigns liaison officers to monitor compliance with minimum human rights standards in third countries.

The GAM was established in 2004 and revised in 2011 as the GAMM, and its main focus is to prevent irregular migration into the EU by emphasising cooperation with third countries. Among the developments mentioned above, the GAMM is significant. With its overarching reference point and conceptual framing of EU external migration policy, its three pillars frame the essentials and priorities of the EU for cooperation with third countries in this policy field: better organising legal migration and fostering well-managed mobility; preventing and combating irregular migration, and eradicating trafficking in human beings; and maximising the development impact of migration (Capesciotti, 2017: 9–11). Although it first targeted the EU's southern neighbourhood, the scope was expanded to the eastern and south-eastern neighbourhood (2006). After this, a series of MobPs were signed with the Eastern European and Caucasus countries. The Intergovernmental Euro-African Dialogue on Migration and Development (Rabat Process) was launched in Rabat in 2006, and another ministerial conference launched in Tripoli among the EU and Africa countries in 2007 (which in 2014 became the Khartoum Process). However, both GAM and GAMM paid limited attention to legal migration and development and instead centred on tackling irregular migration and control (Ibid.), in line with the so-called 'remote control' approach.

The MobPs were important outcomes in this period. They are the main comprehensive and long-term bilateral frameworks for facilitating policy dialogue with third countries (Capesciotti, 2017: 30), which is an important part of the GAM, and then GAMM. The MobPs saw countries classified for the first time according to their potential roles within the EU's externalisation policy. The first MobPs emerged in 2007 with the main focus on readmission agreements and visa facilitation agreements. They are set up on a joint declaration between the EU, interested MS and the third country. The MobPs are negotiated not only by the Commission, the Presidency of the Council, representatives of MS and the third country but also with EU agencies such as Frontex, EASO and Europol (Ibid.: 32).

Compared with the regional dialogues, the MobPs are more bilateral and flexible in order to minimize third countries' reluctance to participate. They are more flexible than regional dialogues and they involve concrete initiatives to decrease the national reluctance of the signatory side. As the European Commission reflects clearly, each MP led visa facilitation and readmission agreements. Thus, the conditionality and the attached incentives are visible (European Commission, 2020b). As the latest country, the MobP was signed in 2016. In total, nine MobPs have been signed as of 2020—with Cape Verde (2008), Moldova (2008), Georgia (2009), Armenia (2011), Morocco (2013), Azerbaijan (2013), Tunisia (2014), Jordan (2014), and Belarus (2016). All are financially supported through the Mobility Partnership Facility (MPF) (Ibid.)

The EU Return Directive was signed in 2008 (and came into force in 2010). Since this time, the conclusion of readmission agreements has risen to the top of the EU agenda, and the EU Pact foresees comprehensive revision of the Directive. The readmission agreements, visa facilitation and visa waiver agreements are closely connected to the MobPs and the EU's return policy. They appear as the necessary tools and incentives of the return policy and provide the political background. Since the 1990s, those clauses are part of international agreements. The

EU completed seventeen readmission agreements (EURAs).¹⁷ As for the incentives, the visa facilitation or exemption provided to the signatory non-EU side of the readmission agreements. The first visa facilitation agreements (VFA) are completed with Russia (2007), Albania (2008), Bosnia and Herzegovina (2008), FYROM (2008), Serbia (2008), Montenegro (2008), Georgia (2011), Moldova (2013), Ukraine (2013), Azerbaijan (2014), Armenia (2014), and Cape Verde (2014) (European Commission, 2020).

Visa exemption or waiver agreements between the EU and a non-EU country provide visa-free travel for their citizens when travelling to the other contracting party's territory for a maximum of three months in any six months period. The EU has several agreements in place, the most salient of which is the Schengen zone and associated countries. Beyond this, the EU has arrangements with Australia, South Korea and Japan. In 2015, the EU signed a short-term visa waiver with St Lucia, the Commonwealth of Dominica, Grenada, St Vincent and the Grenadines, the Republic of Vanuatu, the independent State of Samoa and the Republic of Trinidad and Tobago (ACP, 2015).

In 2010, the EASO was established to support the CEAS. Like Frontex, it has since expanded its cooperation with third countries to assist capacity-building measures, implement RPP/RDPPs and participate in resettlement actions. In 2013, the EASO adopted its External Action Strategy. Accordingly, the external area's priority activities are to support the implementation of RPP/RDPPs and capacity-building activities in third countries and facilitate the related activities of the Directorate General (DG) Home, the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO), and the JHA agencies in the various MS.

3.3. Third Phase: From the State of Exception to the New Normal (2015–present)

After the Arab uprisings broke out in 2011, the arrival of migrants from the Middle East and Africa peaked in 2015. The EU's asylum system proved to be weak in responding to this unexpected mass migration. The Dublin Regulation contributed to an uneven distribution of migrants within Europe and resulted in pressure on the frontline countries. Different MS responded differently, but migration became a top priority on the EU's overall political agenda. The migration pressures at the borders became one of the major challenges for the EU's migration and asylum policies and significantly impacted the external dimension of these policy fields.

In response to the multifaceted challenges posed by Syrian mass migration, the European Commission developed communications on return policy in 2014 and 2015 and the European Agenda on Migration in 2015. The Agenda rests on four pillars: (1) reducing irregular migration, (2) improved border management, (3) a common asylum policy, and (4) a new policy on legal migration. It reinforces the long-standing policy, in place since the early 1990s, to control refugees and other migrant flows before they ever reach the borders of the EU. And in the context of the response to Syrian mass migration, the Agenda re-confirmed the EU's enduring asylum paradox—namely, its “commitment to international protection for refugees and [desire] to keep them away from EU territory” (Ruhmann and FitzGerald, 2016: 7).

¹⁷ The following EURAs had been agreed as of November 2020: Hong Kong SAR (2004), Macao SAR (2004), Sri Lanka (2005), Albania (2006), Russia (2007), Ukraine (2008), FYROM (2008), Bosnia & Herzegovina (2008), Montenegro (2008), Serbia (2008), Moldova (2008), Pakistan (2010), Georgia (2011), Armenia (2014), Azerbaijan (2014), Turkey (2014) and Cape Verde (2014) (European Commission, 2020c)

In terms of special focus, the EU first looks to non-EU states on the Western Balkan migration route and Turkey. Great importance has been given to cooperation with third countries on readmission to increase the EU's policy effectiveness. To address the growing problem of increasing migration flows across the Mediterranean Sea and find a common solution, an international summit was held in Valletta, Malta, in November 2015. It gathered more than 40 European and African heads of state and government to find common ground to respond to migration movements. This summit produced an Action Plan with €1.8 billion in funding support mainly dedicated to combating irregular migration. The EU subsequently renewed its efforts to develop migration partnerships with African countries. In 2016, the European Commission produced a new communication entitled 'Towards a New Partnership Framework with Third Countries under the European Agenda on Migration' (European Commission, 2016).

This communication expanded externalisation of migration control beyond Libya to surrounding sub-Saharan countries, including Ethiopia, Eritrea, and Sudan. It provided an external opening highlighting the need for cooperation and emphasised that "tailored and specific agreements with each country, with full respect for human rights, are also supported" (Ibid.). According to Pastore (2016), this communication introduced four critical changes: 1) new incentives in support of migration policy via policy fields traditionally viewed as domestic (e.g., education, agriculture); 2) the creation of a country-based classification scheme, with some countries (e.g., Ethiopia, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal) given priority; 3) the inclusion of private-sector financing to decrease the burden on the EU and the MS; and 4) finally, the involvement of multilateral groupings (e.g., the G7 and the G20) to underscore the global scope of the external dimension.

Following this communication, the joint Declarations for a Common Agenda on Migration and Mobility (CAMM) were signed between the EU and Ethiopia (2015), Nigeria (2015) and India (2016). Compared to the MobPs, the CAMM appears to be vaguer and seeks to promote new opportunities for cooperation with third countries that have been unwilling to sign readmission agreements or collaborate directly. The CAMMs are even more flexible soft law instruments designed for regional or MobPs that have hitherto proven dysfunctional. They focus on support measures such as data exchange and exchange of best practices, and the like. In particular, they are signed with the countries that have ongoing problems regarding finalisation of readmission agreements. CAMMs are not binding but provide the opportunity for dialogue and cooperation. They are also more suited to differentiated integration because, unlike MobPs (which are multilateral, region-wide and standardised), CAMMs are flexible and bilateral.

One of the most significant recent developments in the recent period is the European Commission's aforementioned new communication "The EU Pact on Migration and Asylum"¹⁸ (the EU Pact), published on 23 September 2020 (European Commission, 2020a). The EU Pact is arguably the first major statement of the post-European migration crisis era and seeks to draw together the key justifications for the EU's ongoing crisis-management decisions and protocols. Overall, the EU Pact reflects the ongoing policy praxis at both the EU and MS levels and confirms that differentiated integration has become the norm in this policy field.

Concerning the third country dimension, one of the most important aspects of this new communication by the European Commission is the return policy. It aims to improve return procedures and strengthen return governance structures. In this regard, the EU Pact emphasises the role of Frontex in terms of supporting return operations and introduces a new mechanism in this area—namely, return sponsorship solidarity measures. It underscores the

¹⁸ The European Commission's communication on "A New Pact on Migration and Asylum" is available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:85ff8b4f-ff13-11ea-b44f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_3&format=PDF (Accessed 4 October 2020).

significance of readmissions and cooperation with third countries in returns. The new return system appears at the heart of it with the proposed new screening system, new procedures such as 'asylum and return border procedure' and foreseen increases in detention. The 'new solidarity mechanism on returns' is supported by 'return sponsorship'. Accordingly, the MSs are given opportunities to select admission or sponsor return. In this framework, promoting effective cooperation with third countries in return and readmission is considered as a part of this new solidarity mechanism. The EU Pact also mentions financial and practical support to assist voluntary returns or leading policy dialogue with non-EU countries on behalf of another MS to facilitate returns.

Thus, third countries' role is emphasised due to return and readmissions requirements starting from the internal new arrangements. The EU Pact mentions that the Voluntary Return and Reintegration Strategy to be proposed later in 2021, which also requires third-country cooperation action. Considering existing problems in finalising and implementing readmission agreements, it states that to improve cooperation, "the EU needs to balance its objectives on migration management with other aspects of mutual interest, in a tailor-made approach" (European Commission, 2020e).

In terms of incentives, the EU Pact mentions mobilisation of "all the relevant tools and policies at its disposal to incentivise cooperation on readmission including better linkages with other development initiatives and national strategies, aiming to build partner countries' capacity and ownership" (Ibid.). It emphasizes that the EU should mobilise all its potential policies, tools and instruments to enhance cooperation on readmission (Ibid.). In this framework, established incentives were mentioned, such as the visa code (as "revised"). The Commission is given the flexibility to keep the other doors open for cooperation with third countries, as the EU Pact "foresees the possibility for the Commission to identify additional measures, including in other policy areas or funding instruments to incentivise and improve cooperation with third countries to facilitate return and readmission". In line with differentiated integration, it envisages EU-third country cooperation that is flexible and tailor-made for each country case.

In parallel to the previously discussed securitisation aspect, the EU Pact references the potential for future crisis and mentions specific instruments for crisis preparedness and management in the field of migration and asylum. Most importantly, it provides an opportunity to implement a faster procedure in times of crisis, and the EU members were allowed "to choose between fulfilling their allocation through either relocation or return sponsorship, and no correction mechanism or flexibility elements are applicable" (European Commission, 2020e). Most importantly, the EU Pact foresees "resilience and flexibility in cases of crisis" and proposes both "opt-in" and "opt-out" possibilities for the MS in any prospective crisis. In case of crisis or force majeure, the blueprint will be available as a flexible tool functioning in full coherence with existing EU crisis management mechanisms (e.g., the Integrated Policy Crisis Response and Civil Protection Mechanism). The EU Pact establishes criteria for determining crisis or force majeure against the possible future crisis and highlights the prospect of migration pressure at the borders, assuming the possibility of unforeseen mass migration and mass asylum claims at some future date.

Two of the most central parts of the EU Pact are externalisation of migration and asylum policy and deepening cooperation with third countries in this field. The EU Pact does not provide a new strategy for cooperation with third countries but only the well-known incentives or tools. However, it highlights a more flexible and balanced approach as showing the potential for differentiated cooperation with source and transit third countries. The emphasis on "balanced, comprehensive and mutually beneficial partnership" suggests the EU recognizes that the existing cooperation mechanism within and outside the EU is unbalanced. Indeed, the Pact further notes that a "tailor-made approach will be based on a joint assessment of the interests of both the EU and its partner countries. It will rely on a mix of the following aspects, taking

into account the specific situation of each partner country or region” (European Commission, 2020e). This indicates the EU’s increasing willingness to embrace differentiated integration and “opt-ins” for the third countries. Indeed, the Pact refers to a “change of paradigm” regarding relations with third countries through terms such as “tailor-made”, “consolidating trust”, and “more balanced approaches”.

Despite its vagueness, the EU Pact establishes a new era in the external dimension of EU migration and asylum policy. Central here is the role of the Commission and the EEAS, which are charged with leading and coordinating for the benefit of all parties. In line with the previously mentioned “three-level game” approach, the EU Pact emphasises the role of various actors, including the EU institutions, the MS and third countries. Regarding the EU institutions, the Commission’s role is enhanced (e.g., to develop better strategies for cooperation or offer new incentives) as is that of Frontex and Europol, given cooperation with third countries will be closely linked to externalisation. Concerning financing, the Multiannual Financial Framework recalls more established tools, but new financial instruments, such as the Neighbourhood Developments and International Cooperation Instruments (NDICI), are mentioned. The NDICI foresees funding to support refugees and migration issues outside of the EU, in particular with the proposed 10% target for migration and migration governance-related actions, which refers to € 79,462 billion (ibid.). Thus, the only differences seem to be differentiated distribution based on tailor-made agreements with third countries and a significant increase in terms of the budget allocation. In this framework, Turkey is mentioned explicitly within the Pact and its related documents (alongside Libya, Niger and Rwanda). Thus, in general, except for the differentiated integration internally for the MSs and externally for the non-EU countries through more mutually beneficial partnership with more generous financial support, the Pact does not provide sound solutions for a better and humanitarian migration and asylum policy but rather reinforces established not very well functioning approaches.

4. The Country Case: Turkey

The EU and Turkey have a long and extremely complicated relationship. Formal relations date back to 1959 when Turkey applied for associate membership in the European Economic Community (EEC). The 1963 Association Agreement between Turkey and the EEC (Ankara Agreement 1963), the Helsinki European Council decision of 1999 granting official candidate status to Turkey and the formal opening of membership negotiations in 2005 are the three critical milestones. Due to the accession process, relations with Turkey have been conducted both through Europeanisation and externalisation. As mentioned earlier, Turkey’s Europeanisation has always been ‘critical’ (Tolay, 2012) and ‘absorption with reservations’ (Özçürümez and Şenses, 2011). However, more differentiated integration and membership became the case after 2015. The EUTS (2016) appears to be a concrete outcome of this shift and exemplifies the new era in the EU’s externalisation policy.

The EU immigration and asylum policy externalisation process towards Turkey officially started with the Helsinki Summit in 1999. Since then, the EU has been one of the critical drivers of Turkish immigration and asylum policy, along with mass migration movements from the Middle East. The main issue regarding the significance of migration and mobility in the EU–Turkey relations have always been irregular transit migration of third-country nationals through Turkey en route to Europe (see, among others, İçduygu, 2003, 2011a, 2011b; Kirişçi, 2003; Gökalp Aras, 2013; Kaya and Marchetti, 2014; Aydın Düzgüt and Tocci, 2015). Regarding Turkey’s immigration and asylum policies, the EU’s demands can be summarised as follows. Turkey must support the EU’s external border control through integrated border management, harmonisation in visa policy and effective implementation of readmission agreements and the lifting of geographical limitations to the 1951 Geneva Convention. In response to the actions

mentioned above, Turkey has been promised capacity-building and financial support, visa exemption, and—if the other membership conditions are fulfilled—full EU membership at the end. Due to the dramatic increase in irregular migration and asylum applications in the EU following the Arab uprisings and the Syrian conflict, Turkey’s role as gatekeeper of “Fortress Europe” has become increasingly important (Benvenuti, 2017: 1). Thus, the EU's focus has expanded intensively to the asylum dimension and has resulted in a shift in EU–Turkey relations and emphasis on new cooperation tools.

Post-2015 developments form the core of the report. However, before turning to these in detail, there is a need to briefly sketch the historical context of EU–Turkey relations in migration and asylum from the perspective of externalisation.

4.1. EU Externalisation Instruments and Turkey

Except for MobPs and CAMMs, the previously mentioned EU externalisation instruments in this policy field have been applied to Turkey. Nevertheless, in place of MobPs and CAMMs, various Turkey-specific instruments both have been introduced, especially after 2015. These include the EU–Turkey Joint Action Plan (2015), the EUTS (2016) and the EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT). Before 2015, more standardised EU externalisation policy and instruments were in operation vis-à-vis Turkey. The Turkey-specific strategies and instruments developed after 2015 reflect the country's increasing importance for controlling both migrant and asylum flows and Turkey’s policy response.

In terms of **the political instruments**, Turkey is a part of both the Prague Process¹⁹ (launched in 2011) and the Budapest Process²⁰ (started in 2013) under the EU’s **regional dialogues**. Both processes focus on irregular migration, readmission, voluntary return and reintegration and capacity development for asylum and international protection. In terms of **bilateral dialogue**, the key items are the Ankara Association Agreement (1963), the Customs Union Agreement (1995), official recognition as a candidate for full membership (1999) and bilateral negotiations for full membership (2005). As an official candidate country, Turkey did not need a **MobP or a CAMM**. Unlike other third countries, the readmission agreement and visa dialogue have been completed as a part of Turkey’s membership process. As the concrete outcomes of this political dialogue, Turkey has agreed on numerous **legal instruments** with the EU, such as the agreements mentioned above and the EU–Turkey Readmission Agreement (2013) and the visa dialogue. The EUTS appears both as a political instrument—indeed, as a bilateral dialogue between Turkey and the European Council—and a specific international agreement, thus a legal instrument.

As a part of the **operational instruments**, Turkey has a special refugee protection programme supported by the EU financed by the FRIT. It has also signed a Memorandum of Understanding (widely used as a working agreement) with Frontex since 2012 (Frontex, 2020a). The following year, the EASO adopted its External Action Strategy, in which cooperation with key third countries—namely, the Western Balkan countries, Turkey and the Middle East and North African (MENA)—were given priority. In Turkey, EASO works closely with the EU Delegation and the individual MS to monitor Turkey's resettlement operations to the EU and advise MS’ resettlement efforts in the Turkish context. Regarding **financial instruments**, Turkey has benefited from many instruments, including the Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA)

¹⁹ Further information is available at: <https://www.pragueprocess.eu/en/> (Accessed 1 November 2020).

²⁰ Further information is available at: <https://www.budapestprocess.org/> (Accessed 7 November 2020).

and the European Instrument for Democracy and Human Rights (EIDHR). Following 2015, the JAP and the EUTS saw a fresh €6 billion assigned to Turkey.

4.1.1. EU–Turkey Relations in the Field of Migration and Asylum Before 2015 (1999–2014)

Up to the 1999 Helsinki European Council, Turkey lacked a unified legal and institutional framework for immigration. However, Turkish policymakers did not prioritise this policy area since Turkey was primarily a transit country at the time. Its transit position was nevertheless important for the EU. Thus, after Helsinki, the need for reforms in this policy field became pressing from the EU side. Europeanisation was visible, and Turkey adopted a set of migration reforms during the 2000s and until 2013 with significant momentum.

As the negotiations for full membership began in 2005, a new phase started in EU–Turkey relations, which significantly impacted migration and asylum. While the EU prepared the Accession Partnership Documents (APDs),²¹ Turkey responded with the National Action Programmes for adopting the EU Acquis (NPAAs).²² The most significant reforms and development regarding Turkey’s migration and asylum policies in line with the EU’s were realized, starting from 2005 (Müftüler Baç 2005: Açıkmeşe, 2010). The Turkish NPAA for asylum and migration signed in 2005 was an important outcome here. Nevertheless, after negotiations for full membership started in 2005, the Turkish government became increasingly critical of the EU approach and even discontinued implementing many EU reform initiatives. Criticism was centred on the EU’s self-interested and narrow-minded security-based perspective; the framing of Turkey as a buffer or ‘dumping zone’ in the fight against irregular migration; the EU’s ignorance of economic, social and political dynamics in Turkey; and the lack of burden-sharing on the part of the EU (Gökalp Aras, 2013). While the membership process has been expanding, the credibility of EU membership has been declining (Açıkmeşe, 2010; Öniş, 2008; Ulusoy, 2005).

Along with these criticisms, Turkey’s migration country profile has been changing, as it shifted from being an emigration country to one of immigration and transit. Therefore, the existing legal and institutional framework proved insufficient and reforms were needed. Thus, reforms have been maintained with high momentum. However, Turkey has continued to resist certain areas, such as maintaining the geographical limitation and providing liberal visa regimes for some countries on the EU’s negative list. Thus, Turkey’s Europeanisation path has not been linear but rather involved resistance (Tolay, 2012: 42). As far as EU–Turkey relations are concerned, conditionality has characterised the approach of both sides, although the EU has largely kept the upper hand.

Syrian mass migration after 2011 provoked significant shifts in immigration and asylum policy for both Turkey and the EU with an impact on EU–Turkey relations more broadly. In 2013, in line with its accession commitments, a new Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP) was enacted, ending Turkey’s highly fragmented migration and international protection legal framework. However, the LFIP did not lift Turkey’s geographical limitation as the EU had

²¹ Four APDs were prepared by the EU in 2011, 2003, 2006 and 2008. Their full texts are available at: https://ab.gov.tr/46226_en.html (Accessed 4 September 2020).

²² The three NPAAs were prepared by Turkey in 2001, 2003 and 2008. Their full texts are available at: https://ab.gov.tr/national-programmes-for-the-adoption-of-the-acquis-npaa-46225_en.html (Accessed 4 September 2020).

sought but introduced a new category ('conditional refugee') and offered the status of 'temporary protection' for Syrian refugees.

In view of the EU's long-standing demands, Brussels and Ankara signed the EU–Turkey Readmission Agreement (EUTRA) in 2013. The EUTRA specifies provisions related to the readmission of nationals from the EU MS and Turkey. It also deals with the readmission of third-country nationals (TCNs) and stateless persons who have entered into, or stayed on, the territory of either side directly arriving from the territory of the other side. The EUTRA marked the moment when Turkey began to use conditionality more intensively in its relations with the EU. Following the signing of the EUTRA, the EU announced the much-expected Roadmap Towards a Visa-Free Regime with Turkey, which contained 72 benchmarks or requirements Turkey was expected to meet to achieve full visa exemption. In response, Turkey prepared its own Annotated Roadmap Towards a Visa-Free Regime that addressed the same matters from Ankara's perspective. Until 2015, both the EUTRA and the visa dialogue with Turkey appeared as standard instruments of the EU. However, while the Balkan countries gained full visa liberalisation in response to signing readmission agreements, as a differentiated case, Turkey had to settle for a roadmap instead.

Within this period, Syrian mass migration influenced Turkish policy in numerous ways. Turkey's initial 'open door policy' welcoming all Syrian nationals fleeing the conflict signalled an assertive policy in the Middle East (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2015 and 2016). After this regional policy failed, Turkey shifted to "isolationism" in the international community, and its foreign policy turned to a policy of "precious loneliness" (Ibid.). Nevertheless, the EU–Turkey relations revived again after 2015 (Gökalp Aras, 2019a, 2019b) and appeared as based on more differentiated integration as well as differentiated membership paths.

4.1.2. Post-2015 Developments in EU–Turkey Relations

The European humanitarian refugee crisis launched a new era both for externalisation and for EU–Turkey relations. After the ratification of the EUTRA (2014), the number of entries at the EU border peaked. In 2015, the EUTRA gained even more importance. However, an agreed transition period meant the EUTRA could not be applied TCNs until 1 October 2017, before which time it applied only to Turkish citizens. Due to the dramatic increase in irregular migration and asylum applications at the EU borders and increasing migratory pressures, Turkey's role as gatekeeper became crucial and resulted in a shift in EU–Turkey relations and the development of new cooperation tools.

The process started with JAP, launched on 29 November 2015 (European Commission, 2015). The JAP managed somehow to reconcile both the EU and Turkey's needs. For its part, Turkey sought enhanced cooperation and acceleration of procedures to readmit irregular migrants who do not need international protection in line with the established bilateral readmission provisions. In response, the EU side highlighted both visa liberation and additional financial support. The highly controversial €3 billion support for Turkey and the FRIT were adopted as a part of the JAP. Following this plan, as an alternative and crisis-driven response for the EUTRA, the EU–Turkey Statement (EUTS) was accepted on 18th March 2016 (European Council, 2016a).

Both the JAP and the EUTS are crisis-based, tailor-made, ad-hoc, political dialogues. that can also be evaluated as a part of bilateral agreements. They are arguably best evaluated as bilateral initiatives that reflect the EU's interest in developing differentiated integration regarding external dimension where flexibility demands it. In particular, the EUTS's controversial legal status by-passes some existing EU procedures and was justified as a response to urgent requirements in crisis conditions. With the EUTS, the European Council

and Turkey briefly agreed to prevent loss of lives in the Aegean Sea, breaking the migrant smuggling networks and opening regular migration methods to replace irregular migration.

The EUTS is the first test case applying the 'safe third country' concept and has been often perceived as a blueprint for future cooperation models with other source and transit countries. The EUTS paved the way for the immediate return of Syrian refugees arriving on Greek islands to Turkey, on the ground that it is defined as a 'safe third country'. According to Article 1 of the EUTS, Turkey agreed to accept the return of all irregular migrants and asylum seekers crossing from Turkey to the Greek islands as of 20 March 2016 whose applications have been declared inadmissible. It also structures the return of Syrians under the 'one-to-one' formula, which states that for every Syrian returned to Turkey from the Greek islands, another Syrian will be resettled in the EU, up to a maximum of 72,000 people (Article 2).

According to Article 24 of the EUTRA, readmission for TCNs, including Syrians, was suspended until 1 October 2017. The date change was requiring an addendum for the EUTRA. However, EUTS brought a solution and accelerated the readmission of TCNs. On 4 April 2016, Turkey accepted the first readmitted group from Greece as a part of the EUTS. However, the EUTRA could not be used for TCNs even after 1 October 2017 (when the transition period ended) because Turkey took administrative measure based on delays regarding the visa exemption process. However, despite that, we cannot talk about effective implementation of the EUTS as planned, but still, this statement appears as an important representative for the differentiated integration arguments and externalisation

Regarding Turkey's measure mentioned above, it was not possible to obtain an official declaration from Turkey (Öztürk and Soykan, 2019) until 22 July 2019, when the Turkish government officially announced the suspension of the EUTRA. Turkey's decision was explained and justified as a response to the EU's sanctioning of Turkey's gas drilling operations in Cypriot waters. However, then Prime Minister Cavusoglu emphasised Turkey's long-standing request, stating the suspension "was not only due to the EU's recent sanctions. The decision was also taken because the EU still had not introduced the agreed-on visa-free regime for Turkish citizens" (Euroactiv, 2019). He added that "the readmission agreement and visa-free deal will be put into effect simultaneously" as clarifying the suspension of only the EUTRA, not the EUTS (Daily Sabah, 2019). However, according to EU websites at the time of writing, the EUTS is still in place, at least officially (European Commission 2020f; EASO 2020). However, it has been clearly seen that the visa liberalisation etc., was not the main issue; but it was a strategical movement from the Turkish side added to the Statement. Both sides are aware that this would not happen soon. Like the EUTRA in general, the EUTS also provides some incentives and mentions upgrading the customs union and re-energising Turkey's accession process to reach full membership. An additional €3 billion to the JAP's aid provided as more generous than the existing financial support such as IPA in terms of incentives.

While the EU has approached Turkey as a distinct case and adopted ad-hoc crisis-based instruments, Turkey has responded by using migration as a foreign policy tool. For example, Turkey began issuing veiled threats to open its borders as early as 2016. However, the significant moves came in 2020. On 28 February, Turkish state actors declared they would open the borders for irregular migrants who would like to pass to the European borders, following attacks against the Turkish Armed Forces in Idlib (Reuters 2020). It was declared that Turkey's borders with Europe would be opened, and Turkey stopped border controls at its EU borders. While Turkey's side provided the updated number of border crossings continuously, the Greek side was undertaking military measures to prevent the entries. The EUTS played an important role in the February 2020 crisis. Interestingly, at no point during the February 2020 crisis did either side call for an end to the EUTS itself. That this often criticized and a barely effective statement was not torn up is a testament to the mutual dependence both Turkey and the EU have on keeping their relationship ticking along, albeit for different reasons.

Despite the simmering tensions and ongoing crises in the relationship, both sides are loath to deal with any fatal blows to cooperative ventures as also showing the bilateral dependency of both sides and both for different reasons.

Furthermore, the EU offered financial support to both Greece and Turkey, although Turkey’s action has been severely criticized. EU Foreign Policy chief Josep Borrell said that “Encouraging refugees and migrants to attempt the illegal crossing into the European Union is not the way for Turkey to push for further support from the European Union” (AP News, 2020). On March 9, 2020, both the EU and Turkey declared the EUTS to be valid and promised to conclude as yet unfinished elements of the agreement (Milliyet, 2020). Furthermore, German Chancellor Angela Merkel expressed her commitment to the EUTS by stating, “We have to eliminate the root causes of migration...That was the main philosophy of the EU-Turkey agreement. I have been advocating for that since 2015, and I will continue to do so in the future. I will make every effort to bring the EU-Turkey Statement to a new level” (AA, 2020a). Although she criticized Turkey’s decision to open its borders for Europe-bound asylum seekers (Ibid.)

As these developments unfolded, immigrants and refugees from various countries, including Syria, accumulated, and thousands gathered at the border areas such as Edirne, Çanakkale, and İzmir, and other land and sea borders with Greece. While they were trying to enter Europe, they faced severe humanitarian tragedies and violations. As of 28 March 2020, most of the migrants had been removed by the authorities from the border area and relocated to nine inland Turkish cities. As the end of the crisis was declared, EU Commission Spokesman Peter Stano stated that “[n]egotiations and evaluations regarding the EU–Turkey Statement continue” (AA, 2020b). The EU Pact also shows that the EU and Turkey can find common ground—or, at least, that they have some motivation to move in this direction. It seems like the focus will be return and readmission; thus, the revitalisation of the EUTS seems to be among their shared priorities.

Table 2: Externalisation Instruments regarding Migration and Asylum Policies for Turkey

Political Instruments	Legal Instruments	Operational Instruments	Financial Instruments
Regional dialogues: the Prague Process (since 2011) and Budapest Process (since 2013)	Migration clauses in ‘global agreements’.	Regional Protection Programmes and Regional Development and Protection Programmes: Regional Refugee Resilience Programme (3R); Resettlement Support Facility in Istanbul (since 2019)	Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA III) for the period 2021–2027
Bilateral dialogues: the Ankara Association Agreement (1963), the Customs Union Agreement (1995), official recognition as a candidate for full membership (1999) and bilateral negotiations for full membership (2005)	Specific international agreements: the EU–Turkey Readmission Agreement (2013) and the visa dialogue. the EU–Turkey Statement (2016)	Frontex Working Arrangements: Memorandum of Understanding (2012)	The Joint Action Plan (JAP)/2015) and the EU–Turkey Statement (2016) provided €6 billion additional as responding to Syrian mass migration
		EASO cooperation: EASO has engaged with the Turkish Directorate General for Migration Management	Civil Society Organisations and Local

		(DGMM) through the exchange of best practices on matters related to asylum since 2014	Authorities Programme (CSO-LA) Global Public Goods and Challenges Programme European Instrument for Democracy and Human Rights (EIDHR) Instrument contributing to Stability and Peace (IcSP)
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5. The Implications of EU Externalisation Policy for Turkey’s Migration and Asylum Policy

It bears repeating that all aspects of the EU’s externalisation policy are designed to keep unwanted populations as far from the EU borders as possible and obtain third-country support for this through incentives. Where entry cannot be prevented or controlled, then readmission and return policies apply, drawing on collaboration with third countries. Looking at Turkey — particularly after 2015 —we see arrivals and migratory pressures have decreased since the EUTS has been in place. From a peak of 10,000 people crossing in a single day in October 2015, daily crossings decreased to an average of 105 people per day in March 2020 (European Commission, 2020f). The number of deaths in the Aegean Sea also decreased from 1,175 to 439 since the EUTS along with the irregular border crossings (recorder as 83,333 in 2019) (Frontex, 2020b: 24). However, the decrease cannot only be explained by the EUTS. Other factors include the completion of the security wall along the Turkey-Syria border, border closures along the Balkan route in 2016, and so on.

In 2019, the European Commission declared the migrant crisis is over due to the above-mentioned decrease regarding the number of entries as stating that “Europe is no longer experiencing the migration crisis we lived in 2015” (The Guardian, 2019). However, as also the EU Pact shows, the crisis period and the decision-making for the state of emergency turn into a new normal in this policy field and used justification for the strengthened return policy. Securitisation remains an important discourse to justify certain extraordinary actions rather than focusing on the root causes behind forced and irregular migration. While the EUTS appears as effective to decrease Eastern Mediterranean border entries, it created further and unexpected effects in Greece and Turkey with further violations against migrants. As the RESPOND Project’s findings reflect, the EU’s externalisation and the ongoing policies of MS after 2015 have resulted in harsher physical and procedural barriers that appear to restrict access to European territory in the first place, block and/or restrict access to asylum procedures, reduce procedural rights and chances for a positive determination, and, lastly, limit venues for integration (RESPOND, 2020). As intimated, the majority of the MSs have strengthened borders and intensified border controls. The various policies and practices so implemented mark a shift to a policy of narrowing access and a general departure from the initial welcoming approach (Ibid.). Specifically, the MSs have introduced new physical and procedural barriers and protocols (such as fact-track or accelerated border procedures) to limit access to national territory, all of which has required cooperation with third countries. In parallel, the EU Pact reflects the deterrence, restriction and return tendency along with the proposed new ‘border procedure’. However, as the implications of the EUTS for Greece have shown, only through the prism of the ‘three-level game’ can the interactions between the internal and external forms of integration, Europeanisation and externalisation be clearly seen.

In terms of returns to Turkey from the Greek islands, the European Commission states that “the pace of returns under the EUTS remains slow. Further actions are still required to address the return processes and cooperation and therefore, increase returns” at the end of the fourth

year of the EUTS (European Commission, 2020f). For Turkey, neither the EUTRA nor the EUTS could be applied as planned. Accordingly, as of March 2020, the total number of returns completed since March 2016 was only 2,735 (Ibid.). The UNHCR (2020b) has offered an alternative figure of 2,140 returns. Turkey's official data confirms the UNHCR numbers, stating there have been 2,139 returns over the same period (DGMM, 2020). The last readmission was completed in March 2020 as a part of the EUTS, and readmissions have been suspended since this date (UNHCR, 2020b). A further 4,030 migrants have returned voluntarily from the islands since June 2016, supported by the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration Programme (AVRR) (Ibid.). From the beginning of 2016 until the end of January 2020, a total of 18,711 migrants have returned voluntarily from the Greek islands and mainland to the country of origin through that programme (European Commission, 2020f). Concerning the EUTS, 27,000 Syrian refugees have been resettled from Turkey to the EU MS (Ibid.). This figure is declared as 27,079 by Turkey in the scope of the "one-to-one formula" as of November 11, 2020 (DGMM, 2020).

There is an increasing tendency in both the EU and Turkey to focus on returns. When it is not possible to keep the unwanted population from border areas, the policy moves —as mentioned—towards deterrence and return. Therefore, the EU's externalisation policy emphasises deportation and returns (voluntary and forced) as reflected in the EU Pact. The return has become the most important and dominant discourse at both the EU and the MSs levels. It results in systematic push-backs and an extensive use of inter-personal violence, as reported in Turkey, Greece, Hungary and Poland, where Frontex has a direct and indirect involvement as the lead EU agency (RESPOND, 2020). The fieldwork of the RESPOND Project shows that following the EUTS; there is a significant increase regarding pushbacks and violence (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2019; Ilias *et al.*, 2019). These push-backs appear as the de-facto implementation or negative impacts of the existing policies.

Similar discourse and practices are also exported to non-EU members as a part of externalisation. For example, there is increasing concern about Syrians' involuntary returns and individual cases of administrative detention and deportation of irregular migrants, especially in Turkey. There has been an increasing focus on return narratives, ad-hoc practices and techniques to promote 'voluntary' returns since 2019. The fear of involuntary return among Syrians in Istanbul increased when Turkey threatened to open its borders to Europe (March 2019), as well as during the Summer of 2019 when the Governor of Istanbul announced that Syrians registered in other cities but staying in Istanbul would be sent back if discovered (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2019). The number of returnees increased after the construction of safe zones at the Syrian border. In this way, the EU externalisation pushes the unwanted population to buffer zones and 'waiting rooms', and third countries mirror this strategy and approach.

Furthermore, Turkey's case has become a reference for 'what works' in EU policy and thus a model of externalisation for other target countries. Other countries have also seen how migration can be used as a foreign policy tool. Following the Syrian mass migration and particularly after the European humanitarian refugee crisis in 2015, Turkey started to use CEM and migration as a foreign policy tool. Turkey has always had a distinctive mode of bargaining, vis-à-vis its Europeanisation process (Gökalp Aras, 2019a).

However, CEM facilitates and important openings for understanding the crisis-related bargains and how they shift existing conditionality and incentive balances and provide certain opportunities for both sides. It is a fact that Turkey appears as beyond an opportunist state as not only exploiting migration crisis as a foreign policy in pursuit of its policy goals against the EU. The February–March 2020 events also represent the first time Turkey deliberately created a refugee and migration crisis at the Turkey-Greece border. In this way, Turkey has used Syrian mass migration as an opportunistic state vis-à-vis the EU by exploiting an existing

migration crisis, not of its direct making in the pursuit of its policy goals. Turkey's conduct shows how third countries have learned to use conditionality to their own advantage but differently according to each side's priorities and expectations. The EU Pact shows this opening with the emphasis on tailor-made and more balanced cooperation with those countries.

However, again further implications become visible such as increasing violation against migrants and asylums, which were seen at the Turkey-Greece border in February–March 2020 and the Moria Refugee Camp in Greece in September 2020. These incidents were used to justify further actions for turning some state of emergencies into the new norms. Those incidents are used for further bargaining by both sides and new arrangements such as the EU Pact. To reach this aim, more or less the similar instruments were benefited until 2015, but then more country-specific and differentiated externalisation have become the case despite the usage of old way and incentives. When the old tools face a deadlock, more informal, ad-hoc and country-specific tools were adopted. It seems both sides are eager to find common ground, as was clearly seen during the February and March 2020 events at the Turkey-Greece border.

In terms of financial support, a total of €6 billion was allocated to Turkey, on top of the €4.7 billion already contracted and €3.2 billion disbursed (European Commission, 2020f). Although Ankara claims that it has spent much more than this amount, the EU Pact offers prospective bargains and financial support signals. In response to the EU's demands, Turkey has been promised capacity-building and financial support, visa exemption, and if the other membership conditions are fulfilled, full EU membership at the end. It seems that established patterns and incentive structures will remain on the table for both sides.

However, concluding full membership is not a priority for either side. Although the EUTS mentions upgrading the Customs Union and re-energising Turkey's accession process to obtain full membership, neither the EU nor Turkey has emphasised full membership as the ultimate goal. Andrea Ott (2017: 11) argues that after 2015, migration and asylum governance became a “compartmentalized policy field” and a sui generis policy space in EU–Turkey relations. She acknowledges that the European refugee crisis significantly shifted the playing field and argues that a period of “new dynamics with old habits” began. As the EU Pact clearly shows, the European Commission will undertake sector-specific cooperation with third countries and Turkey beyond the formal accession perspective. In such cooperation, Turkey will be a part of “one or several coalitions of the willing ... [working] together in specific policy areas”, such as migration, energy, transport, and economic relations, in a more functional and transactional format (Müftüler Baç, 2019). Indeed, since accession might no longer be a credible option for Turkey, Müftüler Baç (2018, 2019) argues that alternative forms of integration have become possible, and ‘differentiated integration’ might be one such option for Turkey. She notes that Turkey will remain anchored to the EU in the absence of full membership and continue to look to this “multilevel, multi-layered polity with different degrees of integration of non-member European countries” as the EU Pact clearly shows. Thus, both sides' ultimate reward seems to be not full membership for Turkey but differentiated and more functional integration in specific policy areas that will invariably include migration.

6. Conclusion

The report has detailed the significant continuities and shifts as well as the changing rationales and actions (and their related instruments) in the externalisation of EU immigration and asylum policy. After 2015, differentiated externalisation—justified by the European humanitarian refugee crisis—has come to the fore, given the increasing securitisation of migration, migratory

pressures, and the different roles and responses of the target countries of externalisation. Among these target countries, Turkey arguably appears to be the most important case. As discussed through the report, Turkey exemplifies both the internal and external dimensions of differentiated integration as a non-EU member that is nonetheless pursuing accession. This differentiation provides the EU with more flexible movement considering the EU institutions and the EU acquis and also deal with the migration and asylum management with third countries according to the different profiles and responses of those actors.

The report also highlights the importance of migration and foreign policy interaction through the selected Turkish case, especially the importance of population mobility for interstate relations, particularly the EU and non-EU countries. It has shown that the EU's external migration policy must be considered in light of the various actors involved in decision-making (or targeted by it), such as the EU institutions, the Member States, and non-EU countries. It thus moves beyond narrow analysis focused on the externalisation policies of the EU or a single European receiving country to understand the dynamic character of migration flows and the evolution of the interactions with restrictive policies.

However, the EU Pact emphasises cooperation with countries of origin and/or transit to contain and control departures and allow for repatriation. It emphasises externalisation and cooperation with third countries and displays an increased tendency towards differentiated integration. On the one hand, it emphasises the strengthening of external EU borders and the capacity of Frontex and strengthened focus on procedures and screenings at the border to narrow access. On the other, it shows an increase in repatriations, returns and prohibition of secondary movements, suggesting a continuation of the observed trend towards securitisation. The EU Pact seems far from having the potential to deliver sustainable solutions or address specific externalisation changes. It has a strong emphasis on tailor-made and more balanced cooperation with third countries regarding return policy. Furthermore, it fundamentally misses the target of increasing respect for fundamental rights and facilitating access to the European protection system (except for vulnerable migrants). Therefore, there is a need for further analysis in general regarding externalisation and EU–Turkey relations.

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